

A NOVEL DEEP LEARNING APPROACH FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF PNEUMONIA

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Abstract

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Pneumonia is a serious respiratory infection that causes the air sacs in the lungs to fill with fluid, leading to difficulty in breathing. It poses a significant public health challenge, particularly in countries like Pakistan, where limited access to healthcare facilities and the high cost of treatment contribute to high prevalence rates, especially among children. Early detection is essential to prevent the rapid spread and severe outcomes of the disease. This study aims to develop an automated pneumonia detection system using deep learning techniques. A pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and the ResNet-50 model were employed to classify chest X-ray images as either normal or pneumonia cases. The system achieved an accuracy of 97% using ResNet-50 and 94% using CNN. A comparative evaluation was also conducted using the YOLO-v5 model, which achieved an accuracy of 84%. The dataset included 6,083 chest X-ray images, with 5,086 used for training and

validation and 223 images collected from a local hospital for testing. The system demonstrated strong performance in distinguishing between normal, viral, and bacterial pneumonia cases. To enhance accessibility, especially in rural areas, the model was deployed through a user-friendly web application called "Pneu Scan," enabling real-time diagnosis based on uploaded chest X-ray images.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia is a serious lung infection and a common cause of death globally. Over 58,000 children in 2019 below the age of five years passed away from pneumonia. In 1990, over 2 million kids lost their lives to pneumonia[1]. In pneumonia, the alveoli are congested with pus and other fluids, damaging the capacity to absorb oxygen from the air we inhale and eject carbon dioxide. It happens when tiny air sacs in our lungs get inflamed. It can be difficult to breath and can cause heat and cough with yellow, green, or bloody mucus. Some common symptoms of pneumonia are cough, fever, shortness of breath and chest pain. Pneumonia has many different causes. The most common one is Streptococcus pneumoniae but there are others too, like Hemophilus influenzae and Mycoplasma pneumoniae. Influenza, COVID-19 and pneumococcal diseases are common causes of pneumonia. It may be serious even in mild conditions making it more frequent in children under 5 years old. It poses a significant health issue and linked to large rates of illness, as well as both temporary and long- standing mortality across peoples of all the groups worldwide. A wide range of pathogens, including bacteria, respiratory viruses, and fungi, can cause this condition, with notable differences in their occurrence based on geographic location [2]. Diagnosing pneumonia involves a combination of

clinical evaluation and diagnostic testing. A chest x-ray is the most important diagnostic tool to confirm pneumonia, as it reveals areas of lung infection as shown in Figure 1.

Figure.1. (a) Showing CXR image normal lungs and (b) CXR image pneumonia positive lungs.

However, it can be misunderstood with other diseases also such as presence of pulmonary edema which is caused by cardiac problems or internal lung bleeding. An expert radiologist may confirm the true diagnosis. But unfortunately, Additional tests may also be performed, such as blood tests to detect infection. In this paper, we use the principles of deep learning, which is a branch of machine learning by employing convolutional neural networks (CNN) trained on normal and pneumonia positive CXR images to correctly identify whether or not a chest X-ray image given to the system is pneumonia positive or not for diagnostic purposes. Machine learning is the method that enhances system performance by acquiring knowledge from experience through computational techniques [3]. Machine learning systems are used to find the irregularities at an early stage of disease diagnosis. Ideal and accurate diagnosis is a critical factor for identifying suitable treatment [4]. Machine learning methods and algorithms that allow the identification of patterns have been used with chest radiography, CT, ultrasound, and MRI as well as with cough and lung sounds to aid pulmonologists in the diagnosis of pneumonia and in clinical decision-making [5].

2. Related Work

In the past, chest X-rays have been used to detect pneumonia, but their interpretation can be subjective and relies on expert radiologists, causing delays and variations in diagnosis, especially in places with limited resources [6]. Lately, the use of techniques or methods of Deep Learning, mostly CNNs, has increased in medical image analysis owing to their higher capability to independently gather and abstract characterized structures from images. [7]. To bridge this gap Dimpy Varshi and colleagues in 2019 created a technique to identify pneumonia by utilizing pre-trained CNN models like VGG16 and DenseNet-169 for extracting features. The method they used resulted in a high level of precision (93.8%), accuracy (95.2%), and recall (97.6%). In 2020,

João Victor and colleagues introduced a CNN architecture with Tensor Flow to identify pneumonia in children's lungs X-ray images. The model reached a proof precision of about 93%, employing early stopping to avoid overfitting. [8]. Çinar, A., Yildirim, M., & Eroğlu, Y. 2020 concentrate on utilizing ResNet50 to distinguish pneumonia. This Model was evaluated against multiple other structures such as DenseNet201, InceptionV3, AlexNet, and GoogleNet. The hybrid model suggested achieved a superior accuracy of 97.22% compared to other designs, proving its effectiveness in punctually and quite diagnosing pneumonia [9]. In 2020, Yue, Zhenjia, Ma, Liangping, Zhang, Runfeng led the research paper on the Comparison and Authentication of models of Deep Learning for the Analysis of Pneumonia. They evaluate five CNN architectures which are ResNet-18, MobileNet, ResNet-50, VGG19, and a traditional Convolutional neural networks to identify pneumonia pediatric chest X-rays using a Kaggle dataset. MobileNet, which features depth wise separable convolutions, outperformed the others with an accuracy of 92.98% and a recall of 98.98%, [10]. Recent developments have also led to deploying models for object detection such as YOLO (You Only Look Once) for medical imaging with real-time detection and localization. Through various studies, it has been seen that YOLO-v5 is able to detect the pneumonia-affected parts in X-ray photos with a decent speed and accuracy albeit with a slight drop compared to deeper CNN models such as ResNet-50.

Methodology

This section outlines the methodology employed for the classification of chest X-ray images to detect pneumonia using deep learning. The core model used in this study is the ResNet-50 convolutional neural network, selected for its proven effectiveness in medical image analysis due to its deep residual learning capabilities. The overall process is divided into the following steps: Data Collection and Preprocessing, Model Selection and Architecture, Model Training and Validation, Testing and Evaluation, Deployment through Web Application.

2.1 Dataset Description

A total of 6,083 pediatric chest X-ray images were used in this study, of which 223 X-ray images were collected from the local Civil Hospital, Hyderabad, and the rest were taken from publicly available Pediatric Chest X-rays from Kaggle [11]. We have organized this dataset into two classes: Normal (containing normal X-ray images) and Pneumonia (containing X-ray images of pneumonia patients). The images contain both Viral and Bacterial X-rays. in Table 1.

Table 1: Illustration of Regional Dataset and Repository Dataset

Images	Normal CXR	Pneumonia CXR	Total
Regional	189	34	223
Public	1585	4275	5860
Total	1774	4309	6083

The dataset gets partitioned into different folders containing training and validation and testing

data collections. The model receives training on 70% of data through 4258 images while 20% equals 1216 images will be used for testing and 10% represents 608 images for validation which is shown in Table 2. This structured split ensures the model is trained effectively, validated during development, and evaluated fairly on unseen data.

Table 2: Data Distribution for Data Training and Testing

Images	Normal CXR	Pneumonia CXR	Total
Train 70%	1241.8	3016.3	4258
Val 10%	177.4	430.9	608
Test 20%	354.8	861.8	1216
Total	1774	4309	6083

2.2 Workflow of Automated Pneumonia Detection Using CNN and ResNet-50

Figure.2. Flowchart Illustrating the Step-By-Step Methodology for Classifying Chest X-Ray Images Using Deep Learning

2.3 Data Preprocessing

To ensure compatibility with deep learning frameworks and improve model performance, several preprocessing steps were performed:

- **Image Resizing:** All images were resized to 150×150 pixels to standardize input dimensions and reduce computational complexity.
- **Normalization:** Pixel values were scaled using Min-Max normalization to a range of [0, 1], which helps speed up convergence during training and stabilizes model performance.
- **Label Encoding:** Binary encoding was applied for initial classification; for future multi-class tasks (normal, bacterial, viral), one-hot encoding was employed to format labels. To reduce overfitting and enhance the model's generalization capability, data augmentation techniques were applied to the training dataset: Horizontal and vertical flipping to simulate image variations, Random rotation between 0° and 30° to introduce spatial variance and Brightness and contrast adjustments to account for lighting inconsistencies in medical imaging. These augmentations helped diversify the training samples and improved the robustness of the model as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure.3. Progressive Preprocessing Steps Applied To A Chest X-Ray Image Raw, Resized (150×150), Normalized, And Brightness-Adjusted For Model Input Standardization.

2.4 Model Implementation

The core model employed in this study is ResNet-50, a 50-layer deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) designed to effectively train very deep networks by utilizing residual learning. CNNs are a class of deep learning models particularly well-suited for analyzing visual data, such as medical images, due to their ability to automatically and adaptively learn spatial hierarchies of features through convolutional layers. ResNet-50, short for Residual Network with 50 layers, introduces skip connections or residual connections that allow gradients to flow through the network more easily during backpropagation, effectively addressing the vanishing gradient problem that commonly occurs in deep networks.

In this study, the ResNet-50 model was initialized with pretrained weights from the ImageNet dataset to leverage the principles of transfer learning, enabling faster convergence and improved performance on the relatively limited pneumonia dataset. Fine-tuning was performed by unfreezing the final layers of the network, allowing them to adapt to the pneumonia classification task while retaining the generalized image features learned in earlier layers. The final classification layer was

customized to handle both binary classification (normal vs. pneumonia) using a sigmoid activation function and multi-class classification (normal, bacterial, viral) using a softmax activation function. Corresponding loss functions included binary cross-entropy for binary tasks and categorical cross-entropy for multi-class tasks.

The model was trained using the FastAI library with a PyTorch backend, utilizing a batch size of 16 over 100 epochs, and employing the Adam optimizer with an automatically selected learning rate. To enhance reliability and prevent overfitting, early stopping and model checkpointing techniques were implemented.

For comparative evaluation, YOLO-v5 (You Only Look Once version 5) was adapted for classification tasks. YOLO is a popular real-time object detection algorithm that detects multiple objects in an image using a single forward pass through the network. Although originally designed for localization and detection, YOLO-v5 was modified by replacing its detection heads with classification layers to predict pneumonia presence. Despite showing strong precision, YOLO-v5 demonstrated lower recall, indicating that it missed several pneumonia cases—making it less dependable for clinical diagnostic use where sensitivity is critical. Both models ResNet-50 and YOLO-v5 were evaluated using standard performance metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, confusion matrix, and learning curves. These metrics helped assess the models' generalization capabilities, detect overfitting or underfitting, and validate their effectiveness in medical image-based pneumonia detection. The evaluation of random test images involves choosing 10 random pictures from the test dataset to qualitatively evaluate the performance of the trained ResNet-50 model. The images undergo preprocessing by resizing them to 150×150 , in alignment with the model's input specifications. The trained model (export.pkl) forecasts the category of each image (NORMAL, BACTERIA, or VIRUS). The outcomes, as depicted in Figure 4 which include the images and their predicted labels, are displayed in a 2×5 grid using Matplotlib. This procedure offers a qualitative confirmation of the model's predictions and insights into its accuracy with unseen data.

Figure .4. Sample Dataset of Chest X-Ray Images with Labels Indicating Normal Cases and Pneumonia Cases (Bacterial and Viral)

3. Results and Analysis

This study used a ResNet-50, CNN and YOLO-v5 architecture to detect pneumonia from chest X-ray images with high accuracy and reliability. The system has produced impressive results in detecting pneumonia, demonstrating the model’s ability to distinguish between healthy and infected lungs. It was further advanced by deploying the model on a user-friendly web interface, enabling remote diagnosis. The system demonstrated strong performance metrics, highlighting the potential of deep learning and AI in supporting early and accurate pneumonia detection in clinical settings.

3.1 RESNET-50 Results

The detection capabilities of ResNet-50 improved due to its work as a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) identifying sophisticated patterns in chest X-ray imagery. ResNet-50 achieved an accuracy of 97%. The system shows accurate identification of healthy lungs and pneumonia-infected lungs because it trained using a broad dataset. Figure 5 shows the performance metrics.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Pneumonia (Class 0)	1.00	0.93	0.96	14
Normal (Class 1)	0.95	1.00	0.97	18
accuracy			0.97	32
macro avg	0.97	0.96	0.97	32
weighted avg	0.97	0.97	0.97	32

Figure.5. Resnet-50 Classification Report

3.2 CNN Results

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Pneumonia (Class 0)	1.00	0.78	0.88	9
Normal (Class 1)	0.92	1.00	0.96	23
accuracy			0.94	32
macro avg	0.96	0.89	0.92	32
weighted avg	0.94	0.94	0.93	32

Figure.6. CNN Classification Report

The Figure 6 shows CNN’s strong performance by yielding 94% accuracy in detecting pneumonia on 32 chest X-rays, with excellent precision (1.00 pneumonia, 0.95 normal) and recall (0.93 pneumonia, 1.00 normal). Balanced F1-scores (0.96–0.97) and consistent averages confirm reliable classification.

3.3 Comparative Analysis with YOLO-v5

The evaluation examined the detection of pneumonia from chest X-ray images by testing YOLO-v5 and ResNet-50 models against each other. YOLO-v5 model delivered an 84% success rate during testing of the test environment shown in Figure 7. The YOLO-v5 model showed small inconsistent results with the ResNet-50 model yet they both delivered satisfactory results for pneumonia diagnosis. The YOLO-v5 model displayed outstanding precision levels with good accuracy in recognizing Normal cases. The recall functionality of this system failed to detect all pneumonia patients resulting in missed actual case identifications. The model ResNet-50 displayed an evenly distributed relation between detection accuracy and detection reliability thus making it dependable for precise pneumonia

Identification. ResNet-50 achieved better performance than YOLO-v5 in the diagnosis area because it reduced diagnostic errors in medical scenarios despite YOLOv5's high prediction accuracy.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Class 0	0.82	1.00	0.90	14
Class 1	1.00	0.60	0.75	10
Class 2	0.78	0.88	0.82	8
accuracy			0.84	32
macro avg	0.87	0.83	0.83	32
weighted avg	0.87	0.84	0.84	32

Figure.7. Classification Report of YOLO-V5 Model

Figure.8. Confusion Matrix for Test Data of 2-classes Showing Predicted vs. True Labels

Figure 8, confusion matrix evaluates a binary classifier, showing 460 TP, 37 FP, 1106 FN, and 1000 TN. The high FN indicates poor recall for Class 1, suggesting difficulty detecting these cases. A clear 2x2 grid would improve interpretation. Key: Class 1 = critical cases, likely pneumonia.

Figure.9. Prediction of Normal, bacterial or viral Pneumonia through Confusion Matrix

This partial confusion matrix shows in a Figure 9 a multi-class classifier's performance across 25 categories, with visible correct predictions (e.g., 442) and errors (e.g., 141). The unclear formatting makes full analysis difficult, but visible numbers suggest varying accuracy across classes. A properly structured matrix would clarify results. And Figure 10, and Figure 11 displays the predicted labels evaluation.

Figure 10 Example chest X-ray images with true and predicted labels for model evaluation of binary class diagnosis.

Figure 11 Visualization of chest X-ray classification results with true and predicted labels for multi-class diagnosis.

This graph shows in Figure 12 the accuracy improvement of a CNN ResNet-50 model over training epochs, reaching near-perfect performance (1.0) by 100 epochs. The steady rise from 0.0 to 1.0 demonstrates effective learning with no apparent overfitting.

Figure 12 Accuracy Graph CNN ResNet-50 (After Fixes)

This graph compares training and testing accuracy of a CNN ResNet-50 model across epochs (20-100), showing how well the model learns versus generalizes. The narrowing gap between curves

suggests good generalization without over-fitting as shown in Figure 13.

Figure.13. Accuracy Graph CNN ResNet-50 (Before Fixes)

This graph shows in Figure 14 tracks a YOLO model's training and testing accuracy across 100 epochs, showing its learning progress and generalization capability. The parallel trend of both curves indicates stable performance without significant overfitting.

Figure.14. Accuracy Graph of YOLO-v5 model

3.4 Discussion

The experimental results clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of deep learning techniques in the automated detection of pneumonia from chest X-ray images. Among the models evaluated, ResNet-50 achieved the highest accuracy of 97%, indicating its superior capability in extracting deep features and handling complex image patterns through residual learning. The custom CNN model also performed well, achieving an accuracy of 94%, which reflects its ability to generalize effectively on the training data. In contrast, YOLO-v5 yielded a lower accuracy of 84%, which, while still respectable, suggests that object detection-based models may not be as well-suited for the subtle feature variations required in pneumonia classification compared to classification-focused architectures like ResNet. The models were particularly effective in distinguishing between normal, viral, and bacterial pneumonia, which is critical for clinical decision-making. The inclusion of both a public dataset and a real-world dataset from Civil Hospital, Hyderabad, validated the robustness and reliability of the proposed system across different data sources. Moreover, deploying the best-performing model (ResNet-50) through the “Pneu Scan” web application increases the practical usability of the system, particularly for remote or underserved areas with limited access to radiological expertise. This not only facilitates early diagnosis but also supports timely treatment interventions, which are essential in reducing pneumonia-related mortality. Overall, the study confirms that deep learning, particularly transfer learning with ResNet-50, offers a powerful and accurate tool for pneumonia detection and can be translated into accessible healthcare solutions through digital platforms.

4. Deployment: PNEU SCAN

The Pneu Scan system's website has been developed to offer an easy-to-use platform for identifying pneumonia through chest X-ray images. It is composed of a Flask/FastAPI back-end to manage AI-based image classification and a React Vite frontend for a comfortable user experience. Users can upload X-ray images to the platform and get real-time diagnostic findings. The Pneumonia Detection System's GUI offers a user friendly interface that assists users to select and upload chest X-ray pictures. The interface makes it easier for medical professionals to use and interpret by prominently displaying categorization findings and confidence scores. Users may assess pneumonia cases more effectively because to this user-friendly design, which guarantees smooth interaction. Figure 15, Figure 16 and Figure 17 displays the outcomes of the effective deployment of this interface, which uses deep learning to diagnose pneumonia while striking a balance between usability and aesthetics.

Figure 15 AI Diagnosis Report Showing "Normal" Result with 100% Confidence. This scan result indicates a normal diagnosis with maximum confidence (100%)

Figure 16 indicate High-severity bacterial pneumonia identified (99.62% confidence). Advanced Diagnostics enable swift, targeted treatment

Figure 17 indicate High-severity viral pneumonia confirmed with 100% accuracy. Time- sensitive treatment now enabled.

To make sure everything works properly, we tested the system's prediction accuracy on real-world datasets, optimize its performance to speed up image processing, and make sure the frontend automatically adjusts to screen sizes so users always have a responsive and consistent experience on any device. The ResNet-50-based CNN model demonstrated high effectiveness in detecting pneumonia from chest X-rays, outperforming YOLO-v5 in terms of recall and F1-score, which are critical for medical diagnosis. Its ability to learn complex patterns and subtle lung abnormalities allowed for accurate classification, even in mild cases. Data augmentation techniques further enhanced generalization and reduced overfitting. While YOLO-v5 offered good precision, it lacked the sensitivity required for reliable pneumonia detection. The deployment of the model through a user-friendly web interface (Pneu Scan) enabled real-time remote diagnosis, supporting faster clinical decision-making. These results highlight the potential of deep learning models like ResNet-50 in assisting radiologists and improving early diagnosis, particularly in resource-limited settings.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of a deep CNN-based system, specifically ResNet-50, for accurately detecting pneumonia from chest X-ray images, achieving a 97% success rate using a dataset of 5,863 labeled images. The system showed strong performance in classification and real-

time diagnosis, further enhanced through a web-based GUI that enables easy use by healthcare professionals. Future work integrate the system with hospital EHRs via DICOM standards, improve diagnostic accuracy through data augmentation, transfer learning, and ensemble methods, and expand its capabilities to detect other lung diseases like COVID-19, TB, and lung cancer. A hierarchical classification model is also being developed to distinguish between bacterial, viral, and fungal pneumonia for more precise diagnostics.

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